

A Method for the Estimation of Lead Volumetrically by Fajan's Method.

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Wellings (*Analyst*, 1933, **58**, 331) suggested a method for the estimation of lead by titrating $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ against standard caustic soda using fluorescein and its derivatives as adsorption indicator (*cf.* also *Analyst*, 1935, **60**, 316). In order to eliminate the difficulty of preparing standard caustic soda solution and to find out a more simplified method, attempts have been made to describe in this paper a volumetric method of estimation of lead, in which standard solutions of sodium carbonate have been employed instead of caustic soda using fluorescein as the adsorption indicator. The precipitated lead salt adsorbs lead ions at the equivalence point or just beyond (*i.e.*, with slight excess of lead ions) and the so-called 'lead body' thus formed adsorbs fluorescein ions from the solution with the formation of a brick-red lead fluoresceinate on the surface of the precipitate. As the solubility of the precipitated lead salt is much below that of lead hydroxide, it appears that the present method will be much more precise than that suggested by Wellings (*loc. cit.*), though the colour change of the indicator is not so pronounced.

Acid solutions of lead should be evaporated to dryness on a water-bath; the slight hydrolysis which might have taken place, will not vitiate the result, as the solubility product of the precipitated lead salt in an excess of carbonate ions is far below than that of the basic salt formed. The solution should not be neutralised with ammonia. The solid residue is then extracted with water and transferred to a conical flask, an excess of known volume of standard sodium carbonate is added to the solution, to which two or three drops of the indicator (0.2% solution of sodium fluoresceinate) have been added. The solution is then titrated with standard solution of lead nitrate (the standardisation being effected by the same solution of sodium carbonate). The lead nitrate

should be added (the reverse process is not so satisfactory) slowly and the solution well shaken continuously. The equivalence point is ascertained by the sudden disappearance of the greenish yellow tinge of fluorescein and simultaneous development of a yellowish-red colouration due to the formation of the dye-precipitate complex of pinkish colour on the surface of the precipitate. It is advisable to take the reading at the point at which further addition of one more drop of lead nitrate will give to the mixture, on shaking, an unmistakable yellowish-red tinge. In very dilute solutions ($0.03N$ to $0.015N$), the yellowish tinge is more prominent than the red and care should be taken during addition of the last few drops. A slight practice will enable the performer to find out the equivalence point with exactness.

The colour change is very delicate and titration results are accurate within 1% error even with $0.02N$ solutions. The concentration of indicator should, however, be consistent with that of the solution titrated. The best results are obtained with solutions of $0.05N$ strength.

It was noticed that the difference between the readings of lead sulphate obtained by the direct method and that estimated by the method described above vary from 0.0032 to 0.0040 , the direct method giving the lower value, and is fairly constant between wide ranges of concentration, *e.g.*, $0.2 N$ to $0.015 N$.

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